

Macronutrient and B vitamin dynamics of Chowan River (North Carolina, U.S.A.) CyanoHABs

Malcolm A. Barnard^{1*}, Haley E. Plaas¹, Ryan W. Paerl², Colleen M. Karl³, W. Christopher Holland⁴, D. Ransom Hardison⁴, Nathan S. Hall¹, Amy N. Bartenfelder¹, Karen L. Rossignol¹, Jeremy S. Braddy¹, Randolph S. Sloup¹, Hans W. Paerl¹

¹ Institute of Marine Sciences, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, Morehead City, 28557 NC, U.S.A.; ² Department of Marine, Earth, and Atmospheric Sciences, North Carolina State University, Raleigh, 27695 NC, U.S.A.; ³ Chowan Edenton Environmental Group, Edenton, 27932 NC, U.S.A.; ⁴ National Oceanic and Atmospheric Association, NCCOS, Beaufort, 28516 NC, U.S.A.

* corresponding author's email: malcolm.a.barnard@gmail.com

Abstract

The Chowan River (CR)-Albemarle Sound Estuary, NC has been plagued by a resurgence of toxigenic cyanobacterial harmful algal blooms (CyanoHABs) since 2015. Both N₂-fixing and Non-N₂-fixing cyanobacteria blooms have occurred in the CR blooms and, in summer 2020, potentially harmful N₂-fixing *Dolichospermum* spp. was dominant. To identify the nutritional drivers of the summer 2020 CyanoHAB, we conducted nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and B vitamin addition experiments and measured N₂-fixation rates using acetylene reduction assays. Cyanobacteria are generally thought to not require external B vitamins, though the opportunistic use of external vitamins may increase metabolism directly or through stimulation of members of the cyanobacterial 'microbiome'. The CR phytoplankton community exhibited N-limitation with a secondary vitamin limitation in NH₄ addition treatments. B vitamin additions influenced the community composition of the CR CyanoHABs by increasing chlorophyte biomass and reducing cyanobacterial biomass. Furthermore, given the high N₂-fixation rates (240 nmol N L⁻¹ h⁻¹), further research is required to evaluate the budgetary importance of N₂-fixation relative to external N inputs and determine the effectiveness of reducing external N loads in reducing the severity of the blooms. The results demonstrate the importance of N in supporting CR CyanoHABs and the need to better understand multiple nutritional drivers of the recurring blooms.

Keywords: Chowan River, cyanoHABs, nitrogen, phosphorus, B vitamins, N₂-fixation

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Introduction

As global populations grow, increased agricultural and industrial production, combined with poor sanitation practices, have led to widespread pollution of freshwater bodies, creating an impending crisis of clean water scarcity world-wide. Excessive inputs of nutrients, mainly nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) have accelerated eutrophication, increased turbidity, promoted O₂ depletion, and reduced biodiversity (Conley *et al.*, 2009). Anthropogenically-driven nutrient over-enrichment also drives proliferation of toxic algal and cyanobacterial harmful algal blooms (CyanoHABs) (Paerl and Barnard, 2020).

The Chowan River (CR) is a large river system plagued by CyanoHABs draining the coastal plain of north-eastern North Carolina, and a major tributary of the Albemarle-Pamlico Sound. Historically, the CR has suffered from massive CyanoHABs of the N₂-fixing cyanobacteria *Dolichospermum* spp. (Gallucci and Paerl, 1983). These blooms continued until the mid-1980s and then largely disappeared until 2013 when they resurfaced. The current CyanoHABs in the CR shift between *Dolichospermum* spp. and *Microcystis* spp. (NC DEQ 2021). In 2019, blooms dominated by *Microcystis* spp. were highly toxic with hepatotoxic cyanotoxin microcystin concentrations up to 620 µg L⁻¹ (WHO “acceptable” drinking water concentrations are < 1 µg L⁻¹, and recreational contact limit is < 10 µg L⁻¹) (NC DHHS, 2019; Chorus and Welker, 2021). In 2020, the CR CyanoHABs were less toxic (< 1 µg L⁻¹ microcystin) and again dominated by the N₂-fixing *Dolichospermum* spp. At this time, it is still unknown what factors are driving these

newly emerging CyanoHABs. One driver may include availability of B-vitamins, given that many bacterioplankton that co-occur and interact with cyanobacteria are reliant on exogenous B-vitamins (Garcia *et al.*, 2015; Paerl *et al.*, 2018) and some *Microcystis* spp. blooms are rich in populations auxotrophic for at least one B-vitamin (Li *et al.*, 2018). It is crucial to understand whether macronutrient and vitamins are driving the CR CyanoHAB bloom dynamics and associated toxin production.

Material and Methods

Water sampling

We performed experimental manipulations of natural CR (Edenton, NC, U.S.A.) phytoplankton communities that were collected from nearshore docks on the 23rd of August 2020. Water was collected using a bucket integrating the top 0.3 m of the water column, dispensed into pre-cleaned (acid washed then flushed with CR water) 20 L carboys, and transported to the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill’s Institute of Marine Sciences in Morehead City, NC, U.S.A.

Bioassay methods

We conducted an *in situ* nutrient addition bioassay experimenting using 4 L pre-cleaned polyethylene Cubitainers® to which well mixed natural CR water was added and supplemented using the methodology described in Barnard *et al.* (2021). To evaluate nutrient limitation, triplicated nutrient addition treatments were supplemented with either 100 µM N KNO₃, 100 µM N NH₄Cl, 50 µM urea (50 µM urea to achieve 100 µM N),

20 μM P as KH_2PO_4 or 100 μM N and 20 μM P added as a combined addition of 100 μM KNO_3 and 20 μM KH_2PO_4 (Table 1). To avoid silica or dissolved inorganic carbon limitation in Cubitainers during the incubation period, we added 50 μM Si as Na_2SiO_3 and 83.25 μM dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) as NaHCO_3 . Vitamin additions were added at f/200 concentrations, which is a 1:100 dilution of f/2 vitamin mix described by Guillard and Ryther (1962). The concentrations of vitamins added in the f/200 vitamin additions were 2.96 nM Vitamin B1, 20.5 pM Vitamin B7, and 3.69 pM Vitamin B12. Incubations were run for 72 h in an outdoor experimental pond at the University of North Carolina's Institute of Marine Sciences.

Pigment analysis

Total phytoplankton biomass was estimated as chlorophyll *a* (Chl *a*) and was collected from each treatment by filtering 50 mL of CR water onto GF/F filters. Filters were frozen at -20°C and subsequently extracted using a tissue grinder in 90% acetone (EPA method 445.0; Arar *et al.*, 1997). Chl *a* in extracts was measured using the non-acidification method of Welschmeyer (1994) on a Turner Designs Trilogy fluorometer calibrated with pure Chl *a* standards (Turner Designs, Sunnyvale, CA, U.S.A.).

Accessory photopigments were used to estimate changes in abundance of various algal groups following experimental treatments. Samples were analyzed by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) using a Shimadzu model LC-20AB HPLC equipped with a SIL-20AC autoinjector and a Shimadzu SPD-M20AC photodiode array spectrophotometric detector (Shimadzu, Columbia, MD, U.S.A.). Pigment extraction

Table 1. Experimental additions added to the triplicate mesocosm experiments. All mesocosms received a 50 μM Si and 83.25 μM DIC in addition to the supplements listed in the table.

Nutrient Addition	Control	+f/200 Vitamins
Control	No additions	+Vit
+100 μM KNO_3	+100 μM N	+100 μM N +Vit
+100 μM NH_4Cl	+100 μM N	+100 μM N +Vit
+50 μM Urea	+100 μM N	+100 μM N +Vit
+20 μM KH_2PO_4	+20 μM P	+ 20 μM P +Vit
+100 μM KNO_3 +20 μM KH_2PO_4	+100 μM N +20 μM P	+100 μM N +20 μM P +Vit

Vit – f/200 concentrations of B1, B7, and B12.

and processing techniques were described by Pinckney *et al.* (2001). Absorption spectra were used to identify photopigments using commercial standards (DHI, Denmark). Contributions of the dominant four algal classes (chlorophytes, cryptophytes, cyanobacteria, and diatoms) to total phytoplankton community in response to nutrient manipulations were calculated using Chemtax (Mackey *et al.*, 1996). The input pigment ratio matrix for the four classes was described in Paerl *et al.* (2014).

Nitrogen fixation

N_2 -fixation (nitrogenase activity) rates were estimated using the acetylene reduction (AR) assay, as described by Paerl *et al.* (1981), by dispensing 50 mL of sample into 70 mL stoppered serum vials, and adding 4 mL of acetylene. Triplicate light and dark bottles, as

well as distilled water blanks were incubated with the bioassay for 4 h during midday, after which 3 mL headspace samples were collected in pre-evacuated blood collection tubes (Covidien, LLC). Aliquots of 0.2 mL gas samples were withdrawn for measurements of ethylene production (from acetylene) by flame ionization gas chromatography using a Shimadzu GC9 gas chromatograph (Shimadzu, Columbia, MD, U.S.A.). Acetylene reduction was converted from nmol ethylene L⁻¹ h⁻¹ to the more biologically relevant nmol N L⁻¹ h⁻¹ using the ratio of 4:1 ethylene:ammonia (Paerl *et al.*, 2014).

Results and Discussion

An *in situ* N₂-fixation rate of 240 nmol N L⁻¹ h⁻¹ occurred on the 7th of July 2020 near the beginning of the bloom and was lower, but still relatively high (38 nmol N L⁻¹ h⁻¹) on the 21st of July 2020 during the peak of the bloom. By August, N₂-fixation could not be detected when samples were collected for the bioassay. Despite the lack of measurable N₂-fixation during the experiment, there was clear N-limitation, with NO₃, NH₄, and urea all stimulating phytoplankton biomass in the CR community (Fig. 1). In addition to alleviating N limitation, the NH₄ additions induced a secondary vitamin limitation in the experiment.

While most of the variation in community structure was related to the macronutrient additions (ANOVA: F = 29.69, p < 1 x 10⁻³³, d. f. = 71), B-vitamin additions decreased the biomass (t = -2.715, p = 0.021, n = 6) and the relative community fraction of cyanobacteria (t = -8.073, p = 0.002, n = 6), while increasing the biomass (t = 3.111, p = 0.013, n = 6) and relative community fraction of chlorophytes

Fig. 1. Chlorophyll *a* response to macronutrient and vitamin additions after 72 h of incubation. Error bars represent standard deviation of replicate values (n = 3).

(t = 4.290, p = 0.004, n = 6). Vitamin additions did not significantly change the biomass or community fraction (Fig. 2) of diatoms (t = 1.350, p = 0.117; t = 1.828, p = 0.064, n = 6) or cryptophytes (t = -1.236, p = 0.136; t = 1.083, p = 0.164, n = 6). These results highlight a potential for a change in external B vitamins to affect the community dynamics of the CR blooms.

In the resurgent CR blooms, P-imitation and N and P co-limitation, observed during the 1970s and 1980s (Kuenzler *et al.*, 1982), have now largely shifted to N-limitation, meaning that N loading reductions may help mitigate the blooms. Despite numerous laboratory culture studies (e.g., Croft *et al.*, 2006), there is very little field evidence supporting the hypothesis that vitamin availability influences freshwater phytoplankton growth at the community level. In the marine environment, B-vitamin additions have been shown to selectively stimulate growth of picophytoplankton (Joglar *et al.*, 2020). This pilot study showed a vitamin addition effect as a decrease in cyanobacterial growth and an increase in chlorophyte growth, but future experiments are needed to verify the effects

Fig. 2. Parity plot of the effects of vitamin addition of phytoplankton community composition as calculated using HPLC-Chemtax analysis. Error bars are standard deviation (n = 3). Points above the 1:1 line indicate the relative abundance of the phytoplankton group with increasing with vitamin additions and vice versa.

of vitamin additions on community structure, as this is one of the only studies to investigate vitamin effects on community structure in freshwater. We found that with NH_4 additions, vitamins were co-limiting, which have been shown in the ocean for B12 (Browning *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, given the high toxicity of previous CR CyanoHABs, vitamin and macronutrient effects on cyanotoxin production in the CR should be investigated. Many commonly occurring chlorophytes are B-vitamin auxotrophs (Paerl *et al.*, 2017), and are generally considered ‘good’ phytoplankton for food webs and ecosystem health. Our experiment suggests that chlorophytes may compete more effectively with cyanobacteria for DIN once B-vitamin supply is sufficient, and indicates that vitamin additions could be

investigated as a potential treatment for the CR CyanoHABs.

Overall, *in situ* bioassays have demonstrated the potentially important roles of B-vitamins on cyanobacterial bloom dynamics and composition as well as the importance of reducing N to control proliferation of the CR CyanoHABs.

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References

- Arar, E. and Collins, G. (1997). US EPA Method 445.0.
- Barnard, M., Chaffin, J., Plaas, H., Boyer, G., *et al.*, (2021). *Toxins* 13, 47.
- Browning, T., Rapp, I., Schlosser, C., Gledhill, M., *et al.*, (2018). *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 45, 6150-6159.
- Chorus, I. and Welker, M. (2021). In: Chorus, I. and Welker, M. (Eds.). *Toxic Cyanobacteria in Water*, 2nd edition. Boca Raton, U.S.A., 13-162.
- Conley, D., Paerl, H., Howarth, R., Boesch, D., *et al.*, (2009). *Science* 323, 1014-1015.
- Croft, M., Warren, M., Smith, A. (2006). *Eukaryotic Cell* 5, 1175-1183.
- Gallucci, K. and Paerl, H. (1983). *Appl. and Env. Microbiol.* 45, 557-562.
- Garcia, S., Buck, M., McMahon, K., Grossart, H., *et al.*, (2015). *Mol. Ecol.* 24, 4449-4459.
- Guillard, R. and Ryther, J. (1962). *Can. J. Microbiol.* 8, 229-239.
- Joglar, V., Prieto, A., Barber-Lluch, E., Hernández-Ruiz, M., *et al.*, (2020). *Biogeosci.* 17, 2807-2823.
- Kuenzler, E., Stone, K., Albert, D. (1982). UNC-WRRI Report 82-186.
- Li, Q., Lin, F., Yang, C., Wang, J., *et al.*, (2018). *Front. Microbiol.* 9, 746.
- Mackey, M., Mackey, D., Higgins, H., Wright, S. (1996). *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 144, 265-283.
- NC DEQ (2021). [Chowan River Basin Water Resources Plan](#).
- NC DHHS. 16 August 2019. [Press Release](#).
- Paerl, H. and Barnard, M. (2020). *Harmful Algae* 96, 101845.
- Paerl, R., Sundh, J., Tan, D., Svenningsen, S., *et al.*, (2018). *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 115, E10447-E10456.
- Paerl, R., Bouget, F., Lozano, J., Vergé, V., *et al.*, (2017). *ISME J.* 11, 753-765.
- Paerl, H., Xu, H., Hall, N., Zhu, G., *et al.*, (2014). *PloS one* 9, e113123.
- Paerl, H., Webb, K., Baker, J., Wiebe, W. (1981). In: Broughton, W. (Ed). *The ecology of nitrogen fixation*, Oxford, UK, 193-240.
- Pinckney, J., Richardson, T., Millie, D., Paerl, H. (2001). *Org. Geochem.* 32, 585-595.
- Welschmeyer, N. (1994). *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 39, 1985-1992.

